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Title: Podcasts for Ecosocial Change: A Study of Environmental Narratives in the English and Spanish Contexts

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Abstract:

In the context of the current ecological crisis, ecosocial podcasts connect environmental degradation, social injustice, and global inequalities, inviting reflection on the need for socio-environmental transformations. This article offers an overview and comparative mapping of ecosocial podcasting based on 571 English and Spanish podcasts on Spotify. It identifies creators and their professional backgrounds, formats, host gender distribution, and topic clusters. Moving beyond alarmist or technical frames, these podcasts present hopeful, action-oriented stories rooted in lived experience. They foster intimate, expert-led discussions that address environmental education, justice, activism, and imaginaries such as degrowth, veganism, and ecofeminism, while incorporating class, race, and gender perspectives. Independent podcasters are the main creators (55.9%). In Latin America, where environmental defence involves significant risks, Spanish-speaking podcasters tend to avoid activist labels, unlike many English-speaking counterparts. Challenges include limited reach beyond niche audiences, algorithmic barriers, and the need for multi-platform strategies to increase visibility and ensure long-term impact.

Keywords: environmental communication, digital narratives, storytelling, activism, environmental justice, traditional ecological knowledge, environmental education, climate change communication.

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